

INGLIZ TILIDA MEVA NOMLARI QATNASHGAN FRAZEOLOGIK IBORALARNING O'ZBEK TILIGA TARJIMASI

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Ushbu tezis tilshunoslikda katta ko'lamni tashkil etuvchi frazeologik birliklarning ingliz va o'zbek tillaridagi tarjimalariga bag'ishlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: frazeologik birliklar, til hodisasi, konnotativ, dennotativ, idiomatik, ekvivalent

Frazeologik birliklar har bir tilning nafaqat og'zaki balki yozma shakl hamda nutqida keng foydalaniladigan til hodisasi hisoblanadi. Frazeologizmlar, shu o'rinda, tildagi lug'at tarkibini hosil etuvchi asosiy tarkibiy qismlardan biridir. Til birligi sifatida ular nutqda namoyon bo'lib, undagi ta'sir etuvchanlik va bo'yoqdorlikni ta'minlaydi. Frazeologizmlar o'sha xalqning madaniyati, madaniy til boyligini hamda jamiyat vakillarining dunyoqarashining o'ziga xosliklarini yoritib beradi. Ma'lum bir tildagi frazeologizmlarni o'rganib, tadqiq qilish juda ham qiziqarli jarayondir. Ular qaysi formada, shaklda ishlatilishidan qat'iy nazar, ma'lum bir o'ziga xos me'yoriy normaga egadir. Aynan shu xususiyat frazeologizmlarni ma'lum bir tildan boshqasiga o'tib ketaverishini qiyinlashtiradi. Yana bir xususiyati, ya'ni, tarkibida asosan ikki va undan ortiq so'zlarning o'zaro birikmasidan tarkib topganligi sirtidan ularni so'z birikmalariga o'xshatib qo'yadi. Hattoki ayrim frazeologik iboralar yoki so'z birikmalari mavjudki, ibora yoki birikma ekanligini payqash anchayin mushkuldir. Aytish joizki, frazeologik iboralar konnotativ, so'z birikmalari esa o'z navbatida, denotative xususiyatga ega va buni matnda, kontekstdan farqlab olish lozim bo'ladi. Shu bois, har qanday so'z birikish hosilasi frazeologizm deb hisoblana olmaydi. Buning uchun, ularda muayyan norma, maxsus belgilari bo'lib, tuzilish, ma'no – mazmuni murakkab, ko'p aspektli til hodisasi sirasiga kirishi lozim bo'ladi. Frazeologik iboralar rivojida qadim-qadimdan xalq tili, madaniyatining ahamiyati juda kattadir. Vaqt o'tgani sayin aynan xalq tilida paydo bo'lgan iboralar bora-bora adabiy til qatlamiga badiiy asarlar, yaratilmalar orqali kirib boraveradi.

Frazeologik iboralar har qanday tilda o'rganilishi qiziq soha bo'lib, so'zma-so'z tarjima qilish va anglash deyarli imkonsizdir. Ular tilga ruh baxshida etadi tilni jonlantiradi, takomillashtishga qiyin sozlar bo'lsada ular o'z jilosi bilan tilda muayyan bir rol o'ynaydi. Asosan, frazeologik birliklar mamlakat, xalqlar tarixi va madaniyatiga uzviy bog'liqdir. Demak, shu kabi xususiyatlari bor bo'lgan

ingliz tilidagi ba'zi idiomatik iboralarni muayyan turlarga ko'ra o'zbek tilida tarjimalari bilan tahlil qilamiz. Bu borada aniq bir turni ajratib olish maqsadga muvofiq bo'lar edi. Masalan, ingliz tilida meva nomlaridan tarkib topgan frazeologik birliklar ham anchayin talaygina bo'lib, o'zbek tilida aynan ekvivalentga ega bo'lganlari yoki umuman ega bo'lmaganlari bor. Shunday ekan ularni topib, ma'nolarini izohlash ushbu tadqiqotimizning mana shu qismida amalga oshiriladi.

Ingliz tilida asosan, olma, malina, shaftoli, qovun, tarvuz kabi meva nomlari frazeologik birikmalar tarkibida ko'p uchraydi. Ba'zi birikmalar ma'nolari kulgili, ba'zilariniki didaktik ya'ni axloqiy tarbiyaviy bo'lsa yana ba'zilari sarkazmga boy ya'ni kinoya va piching bilan yo'g'rilgandir. Biroq, ingliz tilidagi hamma meva komponentli iboralarning ham o'zbek tilida ekvivalentlari mavjud emas. Quyida barchasini ketma-ket ko'rib, tahlil qilib chiqamiz:

“Banana oil” – nosamimiy, bema'ni suhbat

“You are saying I am pretty enough to be a model, stop the banana oil!” –
“Aytmoqchisanki, men model bo'ladigan darajada jozibalimanmi, bema'nigarchilik.”

“To go bananas / to do or lose one's banana” – nihoyatda hayajonlanish yoxud jahli chiqish.

“When you tell him the truth, he will go bananas.” – “Unga haqiqatni aytishing bilan uning jahli chiqib ketadi.”

“Drive someone bananas” – asabiylashtirmoq, aqldan ozdirmoq. Ruhiy holatni hamda insonning emotsional holatida, salomatligida muammo borligini ifodalaydi.

“You are driving me bananas with all those questions.” – “Bu hamma savollaring bilan meni aqldan ozdiryapsan.”

“Have one foot on a banana peel” – banan po'stlog'ida o'z manosida toyib yiqilish emas balki, tasodifiy o'zgarish yo tavakkalda va beqarorlik vaziyatida ishlatiladi.

“Launching a new brand product Sam had his one foot on a banana peel.” –
“Yangi nomli mahsulotni yo'lga qo'yayotib Sem katta tavakkal qildi.”

“Top banana” – boshliq, yetakchi.

“He was born to be a top banana” – U boshliq bo'lish uchun yaratilgan.

“The Big Apple” – AQSH dagi Nyu-York shahrining boshqa bir nomi.

“Sarah is planning to move The Big Apple next month and start a new job.” –
Kelasi oy Sara Nyu-Yorkka ko'chib, yangi ish boshamoqchi.

“A smart apple” – aqlli kishi

“That boy got a perfect score in the exam, he is one smart apple.” – Anavi bola imtihondan a’lo baho olibdi, u zukko ekan.

“An apple-knocker” – to’pori va oddiy qishloq odami

“The city people didn’t want to talk to the farmworkers and called them apple-knockers when they were not around.” – Shaharliklar dehqonlar bilan so’zlashgisi kelmas va ularni o’zlari yo’qligida to’porilar deb chaqirishar edi.

“An apple-polisher” – boshqalarni ko’p maqtab, tilyog’lamalik qilaveradigan inson

“That new worker in the office is such an apple-polisher, he is always sucking up to the boss.” – Ishxonadagi yangi xodim shunaqangi tilyog’lamaku, nuqul boshliqqa yaltoqlanaveradi.

“A bad apple or a rotten apple” – xulqi bilan boshqalarga salbiy ta’sir o’tkazuvchi, axloqsiz. O’zbek tilida ham “chirigan olma” iborasi mavjud bo’lib, ma’nosi jamiyatdagi yomon xulqli insonlarni ifodalaydi.

“One troublesome pupil is like the bad apple infecting others.” – Bir tarbiyasiz o’quvchi yomon axloqi bilan qolganlarni ham buzadi.

“As American as apple pie” – faqatgina Amerika Qo’shma Shtatlariga xos bo’lgan xususiyatlarga ega narsa yoki shaxs.

“My uncle drives a Ford truck and always wears blue jeans, he is as American as apple pie.”

“The apple of one’s eye” – kimningdir suyuqli insoni. O’zbek tilida ham “ko’zning oq-u qorasi” degan frazeologik iboraga ma’nodosh bo’ladi.

“My son is the apple of my eye, he makes me happy whenever I feel miserable.” – O’g’lim ko’zimning oq-u qorasi, qachon ma’yus tortsam u meni quvontiradi.

“Like comparing apples and oranges” – bir – biriga o’xshamagan ikki narsa haqida gap ketganda ishlatiladi. O’zbek tilida “yer-u osmoncha farqli” degan ibora bilan ma’nodoshlik hosil qiladi.

“It can’t be compared who works harder, you or me; I am a teacher and you are a fisherman, and this is just like comparing apples and oranges.” – Kim qattiqroq ishlashini taqqoslab bo’lmaydi, menmi yoki siz; Men o’qituvchi bo’lsam, siz esa baliqchi, bu ikkalasini orasida yer bilan osmoncha farq bor.

“One rotten apple spoils the whole barrel” – o’zbek tilidagi ma’noviy ekvivalenti “Bitta tirroqi qo’y podani buzar”

“Jeremy is the rotten apple that spoils the barrel in our class” – Jeremi sinfimizni buzib turuvchi o’quvchi

“A peach” – ingliz tilida ajoyib, yoqimtoy, yordamparvar inson degan ma’noni ifodalasa, o’zbek tilida esa “shaftoli” deb ko’rimsiz va bo’shang insonlarni masxaralashda foydalaniladi.

“You brought me chocolate? Ah, you are a real peach.”

“A peach of (something) – nimaningdir zo’r, ideal, ajoyib turi”

“Oh my goodness, what a peach of dress! I can’t believe that you could find it at the secondhand store.” – Voy Xudoyim, mana bu ko’ylakni zo’riku! Ikkinchi qo’l bozordan shunaqa ko’ylak topa ollganingga ishongim kelmaydi.

“Pretty as a peach” – ko’rinishi juda jozibador, maftunkor

“Wow, you look pretty as a peach in that new dress.” – Voy, sen bu ko’ylakda juda maftunkor ko’rinyapsan.

“Georgia peach” – shirin, yoqimtoy, mehribon qiz/ayollarga nisbat beriladi. Asosan, Amerika Qo’shma Shtatlarida ishlatiladi.

“Susie is a real Georgia peach”

“Cut your peaches” – davom etaver

“There is no need to follow me all the time. Go cut your own peaches.”

“A plum in your mouth” – Britaniya iborasi bo’lib, yuqori tabaqa vakillari yoki boylar gapiradigan yo’sinda gapirishni ifodalaydi. O’zbek tilida “Og’ziga talqon solib olgan” iborasi ham mavjud bo’lib umuman farqli ma’noni anglatadi, ya’ni “jim turmoq”.

“None of the working men at the wharf want to listen to him, he speaks with a plum in his mouth” – Bandargohdagi biror ishchi uni tinglashni istamadi, u esa xuddi yuqori tabaqa vakillaridek gapirar edi.

“A plum job” – oson va yaxshi daromadli lavozim

“Wow, Mark has really landed a plum job. Now he has no worries about his future retirement years.” – Qoyil, Mark haqiqatda zo’r lavozimga ko’tarildi. Endi kelajakdagi nafaqasi haqida tashvishlanishiga hojat qolmadi.

“Sour grapes” – boshqa kishi haqida yaxshi yangilik eshitgandagi yomon reaksiya “Ah, that’s only sour grapes on your part because they did not offer you any promotion.”

“A cherry on top yoki cherry on the cake” – so’nggi urinish, yakuniy ish

“The weather was terrible on our holiday but the cherry on the cake was when we lost our luggage on the trip home.” – Ta’tilimiz mobaynida ob-havo juda yomon bo’ldi, hammasidan ham, biz uyga qaytishda yuklarimizni yo’qotib qo’ydik.

“A bite at the cherry” – nimagadir erishish uchun hammaga ham nasib etmaydigan imkoniyat

“He definitely wants a bite at the cherry.” – U aniq hammaga ham nasib etavermaydigan imkoniyatni istayapti.

“When life gives you lemons, make lemonade” – hayotda muammo paydo bo’lganda, o’sha yomon sharoitda ham yaxshilik izlab yashash kerak

“Lemon” – to’g’ri ishlaymaydigan transport

“The car dealer sold me a lemon.” – Mashina vositachisi menga to’g’ri yurmaydigan mashinani sotibdida.

Demak, darhaqiqat, ko’pincha mevalardan olma, banan, shaftoli kabilar frazeologik barqaror birikmalarni tarkibini hosil qilishda ishtirok etgan. Buning sababi shu mevalar o’sha til zaminida ancha serhosil va kundalik hayotda ko’p iste’mol qiinadigan mevalar sirasiga kirganligidir. Ingliz tiliga, bu borada, o’zbek tili ham o’xsashlikni namoyon etadi. Chunki ona zaminimizda ham aynan shu mevalar (banandan tashqari) asosan yaxshi hosil qiladi. Shu bois ko’pgina tarkibida meva komponentlari bor frazeologik birliklar o’zbek tilida aynan o’z ekvivalenti yoki kamida ma’nodoshlariga egaligi namoyon bo’ldi.

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